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A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE INTELLECTUAL STRUCTURE OF STUDIES ON SLAVERY IN THE 21ST CENTURY

1Cíntia Cristina Silva de Araújo
2Erivaldo da Silva Carneiro Junior

ABSTRACT

Objective of the study: The aim of the article was to analyze the intellectual structure of publications on slavery within the scope of the Administration. To achieve this objective, the following research questions were proposed: What is the intellectual structure of recent publications on slavery in the business research area? How is the past of slavery remembered (or forgotten) in this century's researches on business research area?

Methodology/approach: We used the quantitative method of scientific mapping that combines bibliometrics and graphic representation. In this process, we extracted publications from the Scopus database and, then, grouped the references using the Bibexcel software. To identify the subgroups and create the visualization map, we used VOSviewer.

Originality/Relevance: Slavery is generally considered to be the dark side of business practices, and for this reason, it is a topic that is still little explored in management research. The relevance of this study is to systematize the academic production of this sensitive topic and to offer scholars and practitioners in the area a detailed analysis of the theoretical foundation of studies on slavery.

Main results: Results indicate that the intellectual structure of studies related to slavery can be grouped into nine pillars that cover several themes, such as heritage tourism, Critical Accounting, Management History and the perpetuation of the legacy of slavery in the globalized world.

Theoretical/methodological contributions (mandatory): Analyzing the repressed memory of slavery in the context of management is necessary and a great opportunity for future research. It is undeniable that slavery is a part of History that cannot be overlooked and this study explores this latent gap in Management studies.

Keywords: Slavery. Forced labor. Business history. Science Mapping. Bibliometric analysis. VOSviewer

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¹Universidade Nove de Julho – UNINOVE, São Paulo, (Brasil). E-mail: cintyaraújo@gmail.com Orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8516-2479>

²Instituição Financeira Banco do Brasil S.A. E-mail: erivaldo_carneiro@yahoo.com.br Orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6337-2819>

UMA ANÁLISE BIBLIOMÉTRICA DA ESTRUTURA INTELECTUAL DOS ESTUDOS SOBRE A ESCRAVIDÃO NO SÉCULO 21

RESUMO

Objetivo do estudo: O objetivo do artigo foi analisar a estrutura intelectual das publicações sobre escravidão no âmbito da Administração. Para atingir este objetivo, foram propostas as seguintes questões de pesquisa: Qual é a estrutura intelectual das publicações recentes sobre escravidão na área de pesquisa em negócios? Como o passado da escravidão é lembrado (ou esquecido) nas pesquisas deste século na área de pesquisa em negócios?

Metodologia/abordagem: Utilizamos o método quantitativo de mapeamento científico que combina bibliometria e representação gráfica. Neste processo, extraímos publicações do banco de dados Scopus e, em seguida, agrupamos as referências utilizando o software Bibexcel. Para identificar os subgrupos e criar o mapa de visualização, utilizamos o VOSviewer.

Originalidade/Relevância: A escravidão é geralmente considerada como o lado negro das práticas de negócios, e por este motivo, é um tema ainda pouco explorado em pesquisas da Administração. A relevância do presente estudo está em sistematizar a produção acadêmica deste tema sensível e em oferecer a estudiosos e praticantes da área uma análise detalhada do alicerce teórico de estudos sobre escravidão.

Principais resultados: Os resultados indicam que a estrutura intelectual dos estudos relacionados à escravidão pode ser agrupada em nove pilares que abrangem diversos temas, como turismo patrimonial, Contabilidade Crítica, História da Administração e a perpetuação do legado da escravidão no mundo globalizado.

Contribuições teóricas/metodológicas: Analisar a memória reprimida da escravidão no contexto da gestão é necessária e uma grande oportunidade para pesquisas futuras. É inegável que a escravidão é uma parte da história que não pode ser esquecida e este estudo explora esta lacuna latente nos estudos em Administração.

Palavras-chave: Escravidão. Trabalho forçado. História da Administração. Mapeamento científico. Análise bibliométrica. VOSviewer.

UN ANÁLISIS BIBLIOMÉTRICO DE LA ESTRUCTURA INTELECTUAL DE LOS ESTUDIOS SOBRE LA ESCLAVITUD EN EL SIGLO XXI

RESUMEN

Objetivo del estudio: El objetivo del artículo fue analizar la estructura intelectual de las publicaciones sobre esclavitud en el ámbito de la Administración. Para lograr este objetivo, se propusieron las siguientes preguntas de investigación: ¿Cuál es la estructura intelectual de las publicaciones recientes sobre la esclavitud en el campo de la investigación empresarial? ¿Cómo se recuerda (u olvida) el pasado de la esclavitud en la investigación de este siglo en el campo de la investigación empresarial?

Metodología / enfoque: Utilizamos el método cuantitativo del mapeo científico que combina bibliometría y representación gráfica. En este proceso, extraemos publicaciones de la base de datos de Scopus y luego agrupamos las referencias utilizando el software Bibexcel. Para identificar los subgrupos y crear el mapa de visualización, usamos VOSviewer.

Originalidad/Relevancia: Generalmente, se considera que la esclavitud es el lado oscuro de las prácticas comerciales y, por esta razón, es un tema que todavía se explora poco en la investigación sobre Administración. La relevancia de este estudio es sistematizar la producción académica de este sensible tema y ofrecer a académicos y practicantes del área un análisis detallado del fundamento teórico de los estudios sobre la esclavitud.

Principales resultados: Los resultados indican que la estructura intelectual de los estudios relacionados con la esclavitud se puede agrupar en nueve pilares que abarcan varios temas, como el turismo patrimonial, la Contabilidad Crítica, la Historia de la Administración y la perpetuación del legado de la esclavitud en el mundo globalizado.

Contribuciones teóricas/metodológicas: Analizar la memoria reprimida de la esclavitud en el contexto de la gestión es necesario y una gran oportunidad para futuras investigaciones. Es innegable que la esclavitud es una parte de la historia que no puede pasarse por alto y este estudio explora esta brecha latente en los estudios de Administración.

Palabras llave: esclavitud; trabajo forzado; Historia de la Administración; mapeo científico . análisis bibliométrico; VOSviewer

INTRODUCTION

Research on the slavery system, its residues and its contemporary forms fundamentally contributes to management and organization studies. Surely, studying problematic issues such as slavery and racism should be part of the research agenda for Latin American academics (Wanderley & Barros, 2018). However, this theme has been neglected in management research, being usually regarded as the dark side of management and organizations (Godfrey, Hassard, O'Connor, Rowlinson, & Ruef, 2016), resulting in the flagrant phenomenon known as the "denial of slavery in management studies" (Cooke, 2003, p. 1895).

Countering this tendency in the management area, scholars have argued that studies on slavery are necessary to integrate the concept of collective memory to organization studies, as well as to examine the idea of corporate responsibility regarding the past of slavery (Godfrey et al., 2016). Furthermore, slavery has lingered in modern business in different forms, from forced labor to human trafficking (Crane, 2013; Quirk, 2006). Slavery is still present, and its abolition, in "all of its forms", has been the goal of different international organizations, such as the United Nations (Weissbrodt, 2002, p. 5).

Therefore, we raise relevant questions for the area of business research area: What is the intellectual structure of recent publications on slavery in the business research area? How is the past of slavery remembered (or forgotten) in this century's researches on business research area?

To answer these questions, we conducted a study following the method of science mapping of slavery-related studies published from 2001 to 2019. Results allowed us to identify the theoretical pillars and the tendencies of researches regarding this intractable subject.

Following this introductory section, we present a brief literature review, followed by the research methodology, research results, discussion and our conclusions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the area of Organizational Studies, there is a poignant denial of slavery. Management history studies are based on events that occurred in ancient, premodern, and contemporary history. However, the slave period is excluded from analyzes and narratives

about the evolution of management practices. The dark side of organizations is omitted, and thus, the narratives and memories about the complicity of organizations with slavery, wars and racism are omitted (Godfrey et al., 2016). For instance, in American studies on Business History, the history of management tends to ignore management and supervisory practices exercised during the American slavery period, although several studies show evidence that southern US plantations already used complex management practices- the American plantation overseers were the first salaried managers, a role very similar to the one played by the factory supervisors under the Taylorist-Fordist paradigm (Jones, Novicevic, Hayek, Humphreys, 2012).

METHODOLOGY

The methodology applied was science mapping, a quantitative method that, despite being considered recent, has been increasingly used to map and synthesize past publications in the management and organization fields (Nosella & Cantarello, 2012; Shafique, 2013). Science mapping combines the use of a bibliometric map and a spatial representation. In fact, the use of bibliometric methods has been recommended as an alternative for systematic literature review and meta-analysis (Zupic & Čater, 2015).

To be more objective and assertive, we followed the procedure recommended by Zupic & Čater (2015), as illustrated in Figure 1.

After defining the research questions and goals, we opted for the bibliometric method of bibliographic coupling, since we aimed to examine the intellectual structure within a limited period – 2001 to 2019 – and to identify emerging themes related to slavery. Besides that, recent publications have not accumulated citations yet, which requires the adoption of this bibliometric method. Then, we extracted publications from the Scopus database, within the business research area, using the following search keys: "slavery", "forced labor", "forced labour", "hard labor", "hard labour", "menial labor", and "menial labour". This preliminary search resulted in 372 publications, including books, articles and reviews. Afterwards, we cleaned the data, excluding works published before 2001, those without the name of the author, and duplicates. To ensure the

accuracy of the number of citations, we grouped the references of the 324 remaining publications, using the bibliometric software Bibexcel (Quevedo-Silva, Santos, Brandão, & Vils, 2016).

After conducting these steps, we realized that publications on slavery or related themes have increased in recent years; from the 324 publications, 164 (50.61%) were published after 2014.

Source: Based on Zupic & Čater (2015)

After adjustments, we used the software VOSviewer to identify the subgroups with the dimension reduction technique of cluster analysis and to create the visualization map. As we created this map on VOSviewer, we included publications with at least five citations. To normalize the differences between the nodes, the software uses the association strength normalization, which is based on the strength of the links between the nodes. After normalization, we identified that within 324 publications, 89 publications shared references.

RESULTS

Network visualization and findings from the cluster analysis

The network map created by VOSviewer presents the analyzed publications as nodes, whereas the links between the nodes represent the similarity between these nodes (documents). As the software uses the distance-based approach, the distance between the nodes indicates their relatedness (Van Eck & Waltman, 2014). Moreover, the bigger the node, the bigger the number of documents that share the same references is.

As we see the network visualization in Figure

2, the software identified nine subgroups (clusters).

Figure 2: Network map based on cluster analysis
Source: Authors

The network map shows that nodes of clusters 3, 6, 7, 9, 5, and 4 are close to each other on the left side of the map, while clusters 1, 2, and 8 are grouped on the other side. This design indicates that the nodes are more related to each other, which can be confirmed as we observe the themes and references they share.

Table 1 presents the main features of the publications included in the nine clusters.

Following, we present an analysis of the nine clusters.

Cluster 1: Conflicting narratives of slavery in heritage tourism

This cluster comprises 14 of the 89 studies of the network: thirteen articles and one book chapter. The central theme is the narrative of former plantations currently being used for tourist purposes. Most articles focus on heritage tourism in the United States; only one of them focuses on heritage sites outside the United States (Giovannetti, 2009). The use of gloomy historical sites for tourist purposes was discussed when concentration camps became

memorials (Beech, 2000). As these 14 articles show, the implementation of museums and tourist exhibitions on former plantations in southern United States has grown, and researchers have identified a conflict between the narratives produced on tourist sites and the real history of slaves and slave owners. For Hanna (2015), the way exhibitions and museums are organized can misrepresent the scenario of forced labor in plantations and dehumanize the people who suffered with the slavery system. Plantation owners and tour guides might present narratives that can trivialize the practices that occurred in these plantations in antebellum US (Alderman & Gentry, 2011). Authors also criticize historians’ and docents’ absence of engagement in offering a didactic and critical narrative that allows visitors to ponder on the impact of slavery today.

Cluster 2: Slavery, heritage tourism and collective memory

This cluster contains 14 articles. Except for Mcdade (2011), cluster 2 mostly discusses slavery heritage, similarly to cluster 1. In fact, some studies

also criticize how exhibitions or tour guides can overlook the long-term impact of slavery (Beech, 2001). Nonetheless, cluster 2 includes more articles addressing heritage tourism in other countries besides the US. Another significant difference is that in cluster 2 we find articles that analyze the role of slavery heritage from the perspective of collective memory: how the narrative adopted in a heritage tourist site can impact the way society will remember

or forget historical events. Therefore, several of them deal with aspects such as reconciliation, collective memory, and nostalgia (Buzinde & Santos, 2008; Teye & Timothy, 2004). It is worth noting the discussion of Eurocentric narratives that whitewashes multicultural inherited societies (Frost, 2004) and the element of dissonant heritage in which different groups tell different stories about the same object or event (Yankholmes & Mckercher, 2015a).

Table 1. The main features of the publications included in the nine clusters

Cluster 1 - Conflicting narratives of slavery in heritage tourism				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context ⁽¹⁾	Cit. ⁽²⁾
Alderman and Gentry (2011)	Applying the concept of affect: the narratives about the enslaved are less emotive than the ones about the slave owners	Affective inequality	Docent-led tour guides in Destrehan Plantation, Louisiana	108
Alderman and Modlin (2015)	Understanding how visitors at plantation museums can help build and shape the meaning and the impact of the narrative	Memory	Museums of Louisiana's River Road plantations	15
Alderman, Butler, and Hanna (2015)	Presenting the special issue of the Journal of Heritage Tourism that focuses on the River Road project	Memory, Legacy	River Road Project (Louisiana)	26
Alderman and Modlin (2008)	Measuring the degree to which the history of slavery and the enslaved are disclosed in the marketing texts of plantation websites	Marginalization of the enslaved, Romanticism of narratives	Tourist plantations in North Carolina	63
Bright and Butler (2015)	Analyzing the evolution of the narratives presented in plantation tourism websites	Whitewashing, Trivialization	Tourist plantations	7
Buzinde and Santos (2009)	Understanding visitors' perceptions on former slave plantations	Perception, Ideology	Hampton Plantation Historic Site and surrounding area	95
Buzinde (2010)	Analyzing the construction of the collective memory in former slave plantations	Collective memory	Tourist plantations in Louisiana	13
Carter (2016)	Analyzing what visitors absorb and perceive from tours in plantation museums	Narrative agents, Marginalization, Romanticism	Laura and Oak Alley plantation museums	24
Dwyer, Butler, and Carter (2013)	Understanding visitors' reaction to the narratives and to historical objects in plantation and civil rights museums	Surrogation	Southern plantation and civil rights museums	43
Giovannetti (2009)	Analyzing the politics behind the representation of slavery in plantation tourist sites in Caribbean and South America	Narrative agents, Teaching as a narrative builder	Plantation sites in Puerto Rico, Cuba, Barbados and Brazil	14
Hanna (2015)	Understanding how difficult it is to include the real history of slavery in the narratives produced by plantation museums	Annihilation, Whitewashing, Surrogation	The exhibition "Slavery at the Oak Alley", in Louisiana	18
Litvin & Brewer (2016)	Criticizing the narratives about slavery presented in plantation museums and historic heritage sites	Memory, Whitewashing	Tourist plantations in Charleston, South Carolina	10

¹ industry sector, country, region, period in history

² number of citations according to Google Scholar – updated on January, 8th, 2020

Potter (2016)	Capturing the complex role of docents as builders of historical narratives on slavery from their own perspective	Teaching as narrative builder	Louisiana plantation homes on River Road	18
Small (2013)	Describing the role and the functioning of slave cabins in plantation museum sites on building narratives on heritage tourism	Annihilation, Marginalization	Southern plantation museums	33
Cluster 2 - Slavery, heritage and collective memory				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context ⁽¹⁾	Cit. ⁽²⁾
Beech (2001)	Analyzing the emerging interest on slavery heritage in the UK that started in the early 2000s	Reconciliation	Slavery heritage sites in Liverpool, Bristol, and Lancaster	28
Buzinde and Santos (2008)	Exploring the dominant narratives in plantation museums sites through the lens of collective memory	Collective memory	Hampton Plantation and State Historic Park (South Carolina)	84
Dann and Potter (2008)	Understanding the emergence of slavery plantation tourism in Barbados	Dark tourism, Thanatourism, Colonialism	Plantation museum sites in Barbados	45
Dann and Seaton (2001)	Analyzing the evolution of slavery heritage tourism across the world	Dark tourism Thanatourism	Slavery plantations and similar tourist sites	303
Essah (2008)	Examining the history and the present use of former structures related to slave trade Europeans built between the 16th and 19th centuries	Reconciliation, Nostalgia	Historic sites in Ghana	50
Frost (2004)	Analyzing how heritage attractions in Australia deal with non-European history	Annihilation, Marginalization, Whitewashing	Pearl Luggers, Broome	25
Gijanto (2011)	Analyzing the conflict between the narrative of the actual history of Atlantic slave trade and the narrative of diaspora tourism based on the novel <i>Roots: The Saga of an American Family</i> (Haley, 1976)	Historic credibility; Romanticized narrative	Diaspora tourism in the villages of Juffure and James Island, Gambia	10
Mcdade (2011)	Applying the framework of entrepreneurship to analyze Liverpool slave merchants as businessmen	Entrepreneurship	Liverpool slave merchants in the mid-18th century	12
Mowatt and Chancellor (2011)	Understanding tourists' perceptions and attitudes towards historical events	Dark tourism	Transatlantic Slave Trade (TAST) tourist sites in Cape Coast Castle, Ghana	132
Seaton (2001)	Analyzing the differences between slavery heritage tourism in the US and in the UK	Thanatourism	Slave Exhibition in Liverpool's Maritime Museum	52
Teye and Timothy (2004)	Analyzing the development of slavery heritage in Ghana	Reconciliation, Nostalgia, Dark tourism	Heritage tourism at Elmina Castle, Ghana	68

Yankholmes and Mckercher (2015b)	Identifying and categorizing visitors of TAST tourist sites based on their knowledge, attitudes, motives, and sensitivity to the historical past of these places	Sensitivity, Reconciliation, Collective memory	TAST tourist sites in Ghana	37
Yankholmes and Mckercher (2015a)	Analyzing slavery heritage through the lens of collective memory and dissonant heritage	Collective memory, Dissonant heritage, Narrative agents	TAST tourist sites in Osu	21
Yankholmes and Akyeampong (2010)	Identifying tourists' perceptions and attitudes and exploring the ethical issues of heritage tourism	Dark tourism, Nostalgia	TAST tourist sites in Osu	64
Cluster 3 - Slavery and the history of Social Sciences and Humanities				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context⁽¹⁾	Cit.⁽²⁾
Bair (2007)	Conducting a systematic analysis of contemporary prison labor in the US	Prison labor as a form of forced labor, Racial segregation	Prison labor in the US	15
Cooke (2003)	Demonstrating the relevance of slavery in the study of management history	Management history, Capitalism	The manager figure in management history	240
Cremschi (2014)	Reconstructing Malthus' moral, normative, and applied ethics regarding population, poverty, sexuality, war, and slavery	Malthusianism, Utilitarianism	Economic and philosophical ethics of the 18th century	24
de la Fuente (2010)	Understanding why Tannenbaum continues to influence the work of modern researchers of race relations and slavery	Colonialism	Anglo and Latin countries	28
DuPlessis (2016)	Examining the global textile commerce in the Atlantic World, which changed consumer behavior and created new economies and societies during the 18th century	Colonialism, Capitalism, Economics	Colonialism and economics history	48
Engerman (2011)	Analyzing the concept of freedom that argues that the ability to make choices is a fundamental element in economy	Freedom, Feminist view on capitalism	Antebellum South (US)	38
Gaido (2006)	Analyzing the development of American capitalism through the lens of Marxism	Historical materialism, Marxism, Imperialism	History of American capitalism	13
Goldin (2016)	Discussing the historical perspective of the concept of human capital focusing on two components: education/training and health	Human capital, Population theory	Human capital and population development between the 18th and the 20th centuries	129
Phillips (2013)	Providing a thorough analysis of the slavery system in the Iberian Peninsula from ancient times to the decline of slavery in the 18th century, including the examination of legal terms of the slavery system, from purchase to manumission	Law system of slavery	Slavery in the Iberian Peninsula	77

Podoshen (2012)	Verifying the differences between African-Americans and non-African-Americans in purchase decisions, specifically regarding word-of-mouth and the impact of the knowledge of companies that once had relationships with the slavery system	Consumer behavior, Consumption patterns, Social responsibility	Automobile industry in the US	74
Ruef (2014)	Analyzing the economic and social transition from slavery to modern capitalism and how this transition impacted the lives of people, organizations, and communities	History of capitalism	Transition from slavery capitalism in South America after the Civil War	30
Schermerhorn (2015)	Presenting a historical analysis of the development of modern American capitalism through the lens of 18th-century slave trade	History of capitalism, Economics history	Economy in antebellum US	68
Vollmers (2003)	Examining the turpentine industry of North Carolina and slave labor in the late antebellum period	Economics history, History of capitalism, Management in slavery	Turpentine industry in antebellum North Carolina	26
Cluster 4 - Contemporary slavery and other residues of slavery in modern management practices				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context⁽¹⁾	Cit.⁽²⁾
Brown (2010)	Criticizing Adam Smith's concept of property	Economic Theory	World economic system	50
Dahan and Gittens (2010)	Arguing that ethical public decision-making may not be based on a single actor (managers, organizations) but on many different key stakeholders	Sociological theory of issue framing	Cocoa industry in West Africa	23
Gold et al. (2015)	Drawing attention to the challenges in supply chain management regarding eliminating modern forms of slavery	Resource-based view (RBV), Dynamic capabilities view, Contingency theory, Institutional theory, Supply chain management (SCM)	International supply chain	76
Hayek et al. (2010)	Analyzing the period of slavery by focusing on the phenomenon of paternalistic leadership by Joseph E. Davis during slavery in the US	Leadership Theory	Antebellum period of slavery in the US	33
Jones et al. (2012)	Establishing and tracing the roots of African-American management by examining managerial practices and experiences of an emancipated former slave who eventually became a plantation manager and owner	Leadership Theory	Slavery in the US during the 1865-1870 period	11
Ma et al. (2015)	Assessing the results of initiatives to abolish slavery and human trafficking from supply chain in manufacturing and retail after the legislation of the California Transparency in Supply Chains Act (CTSCA)	Human trafficking, SCM, Forced labor	Apparel retail and apparel manufacturing companies based in the US	14

Magnan, Fawcett, and Alcantar (2011)	Analyzing the maturity of conduct codes from apparel, retail and other manufacturing businesses	Corporate social responsibility (CSR), SCM, Reputation risk	Apparel and retail business	18
New (2015)	Examining modern slavery in the supply chain and how this practice challenges the conventional thinking and practice of corporate social responsibility	CSR, SCM	UK agriculture	64
Osterhammel (2014)	Analyzing the different (complex and powerful) forces that influenced the transformations during the 19th century	Economics history	Economic and political changes in the 19th century	572
Robinson (2002)	Identifying patterns of gender and familial-status discrimination	Racism, Gender discrimination	Mortgage lending market in the US	30
Winter and Lasch (2016)	Examining how companies apply environmental and social criteria in supplier evaluation	CSR	Fashion and apparel industry	60
Cluster 5 – The legacy of slavery in social issues of today’s globalized world				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context⁽¹⁾	Cit.⁽²⁾
Burity (2008)	Arguing that globalization can give rise to economic powers that can either reinforce or revert historical social inequalities	Imperialism, Colonialism, Capitalism	The effects of globalization in Brazil	17
Busse and Braun (2003)	Assessing the extent of forced labor in different countries and how forced labor affects foreign direct investment (FDI)	Contemporary forms of forced labor	Labor standards on exports of unskilled-labor-intensive goods	63
Campo, Mastin, and Frazer (2004)	Assessing public opinion regarding slavery reparations and forms of compensation	Historical reparation and compensation	State university in southern US	16
Crane (2013)	Demonstrating that slavery is a management practice due to factors that make it an institutional and competitive practice, and because organizations can isolate themselves from external pressures	Legitimacy, Institutional theory	Modern slavery as a management practice	201
Duplessis (2004)	Examining the efficiency of the International Labor Organization (ILO) Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work on dealing with the challenges of globalization	Globalization, Institutional theory, Labor rights	Rights at work in a globalized economy	29
Giusta, Tommaso, and Strøm (2008)	Developing a theoretical model for the commercial sex industry based on data collected from a database of trafficked women	Reputation cost, Prostitution, Human trafficking, Sex slavery	Sex market in developed countries	37
Jakobsson and Kotsadam (2013)	Showing that human trafficking for commercial sex is more frequent in countries where prostitution is legalized than in countries where it is illegal	Human trafficking, Labor rights, Sex slavery	Human trafficking for commercial sex in Europe	178
Kong (2006)	Investigating the complexity of female prostitutes’ reality in Hong Kong using the oral history method	Forced labor, Body politics	Erotic labor in Hong Kong	99

Maul (2016)	Exploring the historical and political factors that impacted the debate about forced labor in the 20th century and the creation of the ILO	Colonialism, Human rights, Decolonization, Labor history	Historical events of the implementation of the ILO	83
Neumayer and Soysa (2007)	Discussing women's labor rights and their exposition to forced labor at the perspective of globalization	Feminism, Labor rights, Globalization	Women's economic rights in the US	108
Pennington, Ball, Hampton, and Soulakova (2009)	Analyzing human trafficking as a marketing system and its social effects	Human trafficking, forced labor, Marketing system	Human trafficking for sex trade in Belarus, Bulgaria, Moldova, Romania, and Ukraine	53
Cluster 6 - The role of accounting in the 19th-century slavery system				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context⁽¹⁾	Cit.⁽²⁾
Fleischman (2004)	Analyzing how accounting influenced the maintenance of slavery	Accounting history, Critical accounting theory	Slavery in plantations in the US and in the British West Indies (BWI)	23
Fleischman, Oldroyd, and Tyson (2011)	Analyzing the impact of accounting and other quantitative disciplines on labor control practices during the transition from slavery to wage labor in the US and in the BWI	Management history, Accounting history	Transition from slavery in the US and in the BWI	21
Fleischman, Oldroyd, and Tyson (2004)	Examining the role of accounting in the management of slaves in plantations in the period before the American Civil War and the emancipation of the BWI	Theory of Accounting History	Plantations in the US and in the BWI	62
Fleischman and Tyson (2004)	Illustrating how accounting practices of measurement, evaluation, and classification served slave owners and sustained slavery institutions	Critical accounting theory, Accounting history	Southern plantations in antebellum US	106
Fleischman and Tyson (2002)	Analyzing the role of accounting the commoditization, objectification, and dehumanization of slaves	Accounting history, Critical accounting theory	Plantations in the US and in the BWI	22
Hollister and Schultz (2010)	Analyzing the period of slavery and rural emancipation based on accounting records	Accounting history	Slavery and emancipation in rural New York	19
Macintosh (2009)	Affirming the relevance of accounting history for building a more critical theory of accounting	Critical accounting history, Accounting history	Genealogy of accounting	42
Oldroyd et al. (2008)	Analyzing the culpability of accounting users and practitioners in the practice of slavery	Critical accounting history, Virtue theory	Slavery in the British Empire and in antebellum US	56
Tyson et al. (2005)	Describing the nature and role of accounting during apprenticeship	Critical accounting history	Transition from forced to wage labor in the BWI (1834-1838)	54
Cluster 7 - The practice of slavery in the ancient and modern world				

Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context ⁽¹⁾	Cit. ⁽²⁾
Anner (2007)	Analyzing the evolution of labor union and labor actions in El Salvador and Brazil	Unions, Labor history	Salvadoran export apparel industry and Brazilian automobile industry	22
Barlev (2006)	Analyzing the Biblical statement of accountability presented by Moses to the Israelites in the exodus from Egypt	Leadership theory, Accounting history	Period of the Exodus (1200 BC)	23
Dolan (2005)	Examining ethical views of British consumers and retailers towards Kenya's luxury vegetable trade and the narratives inherited from 19th-century colonialism	Consumer behavior, Colonialism, Imperialism	Consumption of African vegetables in the UK	68
Freedman (2008)	Discussing the Chicago School's views on economy and their position against the Keynesian thought	Liberal economic theory	Chicago counterrevolution school	33
Godfrey (2016)	Emphasizing the importance of organizational history in organization studies	Organization history	Organization studies	64
Perrow (2009)	Analyzing the development of American society through the development of corporate capitalism	Economics theory, Institutional theory, Power relations, History of capitalism, Corporate capitalism	American corporate society	598
Rodet (2014)	Analyzing the impact of French colonization in the practice of forced labor through the lens of gender standards	Gender perspective, Labor rights, Colonialism	French colonization in Sudan (1919–1946)	3
Ruef and Harness (2009)	Analyzing management practices in the slavery system of agrarian Roman Republic and antebellum US	Agency Theory, Management theory, Management history	Slavery system in the Roman Republic and antebellum US	19
Cluster 8 - Rupturing relations with the dark side of history and dealing with its vestiges				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context ⁽¹⁾	Cit. ⁽²⁾
(Brown, 2013)	Analyzing the role of museum shops in dark tourist sites and the conflicting ideology of selling products in these locations	Dark tourism	Museum shops in dark tourist sites	35
(Lohrke, Ahlstrom, & Bruton, 2012)	Analyzing turnaround strategies by understanding the history of organization turnaround employed by the US government during the Civil War	Turnaround management, Strategic management	Organizational turnaround of the US government during the Civil War	14
(Lynch & Alberti, 2010)	Analyzing the vestiges of institutional racism in race-related cultural exhibitions	Institutional racism	"Revealing Histories: Myths about Race" exhibition at the Manchester Museum, UK	168
(Mittal & Weingast, 2011)	Developing and applying the theory of self-enforcing constitutions to the reality of early US	Theory of self-enforcing constitutions, Constitutional democracy	Slavery in the US	83

(Picard, 2006)	Analyzing festival boom as symbolism of rupture and transition in international tourism	International tourism, Life crisis, Symbolism	The Abolition of Slavery Day Festival, in La Réunion	8
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Cluster 9 - Corporate culture as a form of domination				
Authors	Main Objective	Reference Theory	Context ⁽¹⁾	Cit. ⁽²⁾
Adanhounme (2011)	Exploring the extent to which CSR in African organizations reproduces the colonialism that imposed Western mandate over local communities	Corporate social responsibility, Postcolonialism, Colonialism, Marginalization	Mining plant in Ghana	36
Fleming (2013)	Discussing the totalitarian aspiration of corporate culturalism by comparing the works of Willmott (1993) and Orwell (2011)	Organization culture, Corporate culture, Totalitarianism	Corporate culture in contemporary management	56
Willmott (2003)	Revisiting Willmott's (1993) idea of totalitarianism in corporate culture and its relevance to contemporary and "post-bureaucracy" management	Corporate culture, Organization culture, Corporate culturalism, Totalitarianism	Corporate culture in contemporary management, post-bureaucracy era	48
Willmott (2013)	Revisiting Willmott's (1993) idea of totalitarianism in corporate culture and its relevance to contemporary management and organization studies, as well as to higher education	Corporate culture, Organization culture, Corporate culturalism, Normative control	Corporate culture in contemporary management	27

Source: Authors

¹ industry sector, country, region, period in history

² number of citations according to Google Scholar – updated on January, 8th, 2020

Cluster 3: Slavery and the history of Social Sciences and Humanities

This cluster includes five articles, seven books and one book chapter. Several of these publications address the role of slavery in the history of the main areas of Social Sciences and Humanities (Economics, Law, Management, Sociology). The book by DuPlessis (2016), for instance, discusses how the 18th-century global textile trade imposed European clothing standards upon Africans and natives. (Armstrong, 2018) examines the global textile commerce in the Atlantic World, which changed consumer behavior and created new economies and societies during the 18th century (DuPlessis, 2016).

Regarding the history of capitalism, there are interesting empirical studies that discuss the role and the legacy of slavery in race and class relations (Ruef, 2014), as well as the transition from agrarian to industrial capitalism (Schermerhorn, 2015).

Finally, studies analyze management practices used to control slaves in industries (Vollmers, 2003) and the inexplicable exclusion of slavery from management history (Cooke, 2003). The area of marketing is also analyzed, as Podoshen (2012) studies consumer behavior of non-African and African-Americans towards companies that once had any relationship to the slavery system.

Cluster 4: Contemporary slavery and other residues of slavery in modern management practices

This cluster comprises nine articles and two books, with themes ranging from the leadership exercised by plantation owners who enslaved blacks from Africa in the US (Hayek, Novicevic, Humphreys, & Jones, 2010) to current issues such as modern slavery in the supply chain (Gold, Trautrim, & Trodd, 2015). Aspects such as sustainability, corporate social responsibility, image risk, ethics and integrity are also present, indicating that discussions which combat slavery are present today. In fact, some studies analyze the impact of the implementation of the California Transparency in Supply Chains Act (CTSCA) as an initiative to abolish forced labor and human trafficking (Ma, Lee, & Goerlitz, 2015). We

also found discussions on the different Economics schools (Chicago School and Keynesianism) and how they oppose Adam Smith's concept of capital accumulation (Brown, 2010).

Cluster 5: The legacy of slavery in social issues of today's globalized world

The fifth cluster contains ten articles and one book. The articles in this group discuss the legacy of slavery at different levels of today's society and how it is being dealt with or even overlooked. First, we find studies on the new forms of slavery and forced labor. Published in the renowned Academy of Management Review, Crane (2013) reckons that economic and institutional conditions sustain slavery as a business practice. Despite its illegality and illegitimacy, the practice of forced labor is profitable (Busse & Braun, 2003), and organizations are able to isolate themselves from external pressures. Still within this scope, there are studies on labor rights for women, human trafficking and the results of the implementation of the International Labor Organization (ILO) as a global initiative to eradicate forced labor (Duplessis, 2004).

Finally, this cluster includes studies which infer that globalization reinforces social inequalities rooted in the historical legacy of slavery and that this legacy affects a minority group, with less voice and influence (Burity, 2008; Maul, 2016).

Cluster 6: The role of accounting in the 19th-century slavery system

Comprising nine articles, cluster 6 discusses how accounting was used in antebellum US and in the British West Indies. Aspects such as the influence of accounting on the maintenance of slavery, control of the work of slaves and the evaluation of slaves as accounting assets were also found in the documents analyzed (Fleischman, 2004). Accounting also served as an instrument for maintaining slavery in plantations in northern US (Hollister & Schultz, 2010). It is worth highlighting the publications discussing the critical and ethical perspectives of accounting and its fundamental role in the transition from forced to wage labor (Oldroyd, Fleischman, & Tyson, 2008).

Cluster 7: The practice of slavery in the ancient and modern worlds

In cluster 7, we find six articles and two books. Here, studies cover the practice of slavery in the ancient and modern worlds. Ruef and Harness (2009) analyze the distinction between "modern" and "pre-modern" management thought. Another theme found in this cluster is organization history. Studies argue that it should focus on larger issues concerning management theory by integrating the historical dynamics that affect smaller entrepreneurs and traditionally marginalized groups (Godfrey et al., 2016). There are also discussions about social organizations that influence the improvement of labor relations, such as unions (Anner, 2007), and how Central and South America dealt with the new challenges of labor activities and unionization.

Cluster 8: Rupturing relations with the dark side of history and dealing with its vestiges

The eighth cluster contains four articles and one book chapter. This cluster discusses cultural elements represented by the remaining memories of slavery. For instance, Lynch and Alberti (2010) discuss the vestiges of institutional racism in race-related cultural exhibitions. Another aspect of cultural-related issues is Brown's (2013) article that analyzes the complexity of the sales operations of museums located in areas related to slave trade. Finally, the celebration of the memory of ancestors is one characteristic of the festivities presently promoted by the black community as a symbol of rupture (Picard, 2006). The cluster also includes studies on Law (self-enforcement) and turnaround management.

Cluster 9: Corporate culture as a form of domination

Cluster 9 comprises four articles, which have as a common line of thought elements related to corporate culturalism. Fleming (2013) and Willmott (2003; 2013) defend that organizational culture and culture management present traces of totalitarianism, therefore are tools to make workers follow organizational goals and values to the detriment of their own. Corporate social responsibility policies in postcolonial African

countries can be discriminatory and discretionary, which causes them to perpetuate a colonialist strategy.

DISCUSSION

As intended, the science mapping provided results that were useful to answer the research questions proposed for this paper.

What is the intellectual structure of recent publications on slavery in the business research area? Results of the bibliographic method of cluster analysis identified nine clusters within slavery-related publications, and these clusters can be referred to as pillars. As we analyze these nine pillars, it is possible to deduce that the theme of slavery is relevant and has been addressed in different forms. Another interesting result is that the practice of slavery has not only lingered in modern organizations, but it has also spread among several levels of management and international businesses. The content of the studies analyzed also show that minorities and underprivileged groups are more exposed to human trafficking, forced labor in sex commerce and labor discrimination. The pillar of contemporary slavery and the legacy of slavery demonstrates that the issue is so flagrant that it has prompted international organizations to create specific initiatives, such as the ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work and the efforts sponsored by the United Nations. Finally, it is important to emphasize that the intellectual structure of publications suggests the increasing interest in slavery heritage tourism in countries affected by the slavery system that endured until the 19th century.

How is the past of slavery remembered (or forgotten this century's researches on business research area? Results suggest that studies on slavery and other related topics have gained interest in recent years. By analyzing the results, we can conclude that such an interest is relevant in different areas of management research, such as management history, critical accounting history, supply chain, tourism, and organization studies. However, as argued in previous studies, the legacy of slavery in management practices still lacks attention: there is a need for more studies that evidence the role of the slavery system in

modern management and in the development of the role of managers. In fact, a pillar of the intellectual structure discusses the concept of organizational culture as a form of domination in modern management. Another aspect that is worth reporting is that most studies present a qualitative or theoretical approach, which denotes an opportunity for discussion: Is a qualitative approach more appropriate for this type of theme or is there room for quantitative studies which have not yet been explored?

CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to identify and analyze the intellectual structure of publications on slavery in the management research area. To accomplish this goal, we conducted a science mapping of slavery-related publications. Results indicate that the intellectual structure can be grouped into nine pillars, namely, conflicting narratives of slavery in heritage tourism; slavery, heritage tourism and collective memory; slavery and the

history of Social Sciences and Humanities; contemporary slavery and other residues of slavery in management practices; the legacy of slavery in social issues of today's globalized world; the role of accounting in the 19th-century slavery system; the practice of slavery in the ancient and modern worlds; rupturing relations with the dark side of history and dealing with its vestiges; and corporate culture as a form of domination.

Although we believe that the methodological approach adopted in this research allowed us to perform an objective analysis, we see the need for adjustments in the bibliographic data as a limitation. Besides, since we used an international database, we could not analyze Brazilian publications. In fact, analyzing the repressed memory of Brazilian slavery (Santos, 2008) in the context of management is necessary and a great opportunity for future research. It is undeniable that slavery is a part of history that cannot be overlooked.

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